

Birsa Dhan 107, a high-yielding and early maturing variety for the upland regions of Bihar, India

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Birsa Dhan 107 (IET12503), a pedigree selection from mutant Gora (G) IAC25 from the Rice Research Scheme of BAU, was released by the Bihar State Variety Release Committee in 1995 and by the Central Variety Release Committee in 1996 for general cultivation in the uplands of Chotanagpur and the Santhal Parganas region of Bihar.

It is a semidwarf variety with compact and long panicles but short bold grains with white kernel. It matures in 90-95 d. The variety is resistant to blast and bacterial blight but is moderately resistant to *Helminthosporium* under field conditions. It also tolerates drought under field conditions.

As a direct-seeded kharif crop, Birsa Dhan 107 continuously outyielded Birsa Dhan 101 (check) and Birsa Gora 102 (local check) in station trials for 3 yr (Table 1). Birsa Dhan 107 was also tested in the All-India Coordinated Trial and found superior in yield compared with national checks Heera, Sathari, and Aditya (Table 2).

Birsa Dhan 107 does not lodge or shatter and is highly responsive to fertilizers. It is suitable for direct seeding and is the most promising elite variety for cultivation in the upland plateau region of Bihar. It is also suitable for transplanted conditions in medium-elevation lands.

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Table 1. Yield performance of Birsa Dhan 107 in station trials conducted for 3 yr at Kanke Center.

Entry	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
	1988-89	1989-90	1993-94	Av
Birsa Dhan 107 ^a	18.1	4.2	0.9	2.7
Birsa Dhan 101 (check)	1.6	3.8	0.8	2.1
Birsa Gora 102 (local check)	2.4	2.9	1.3	2.2

^aIET12503.

Table 2. Performance of Birsa Dhan 107 in the All-India Coordinated Trials conducted through the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, 1990-93.

Entry	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
	1990-91	1991-92	1992-93	Av
Birsa Dhan 107	3.8	1.8	1.8	2.4
Heera ^a	-	1.5	1.5	1.5
Sathari ^a	3.0	1.5	-	2.2
Aditya ^a	-	-	1.9	1.9
Birsa Gora 102 (local check)	3.3	1.8	2.0	2.4

^aNational check.

Jaldi Dhan 8, an improved and potential source of wide compatibility for hybrid rice breeding

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Exploitation of wide compatibility (WC) gene(s) is an effective approach to overcome sterility barriers among indica/japonica crosses. The materials studied included four early improved japonica and seven indica lines including two WC varieties—Dular and Nagina 22 (N22), accessions collected from the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack, India. Two improved lines, Jaldi Dhan 6 (JD6) and JD8,

were derived from a cross between the induced mutant of Dular and N22.

The crossing program between indica and japonica lines was undertaken in the 1995 dry season at CRRRI, Cuttack. Four F₁s, developed with JD8 as common parents, were also studied in the 1996 wet season.

Mean and range values for spikelet fertility of 26 cross combinations showed

a high degree of spikelet fertility in F₁ with N22, Dular, and JD8 when it is used as a parent. All parental lines except Heera had more than 80% spikelet fertility (see table). Cross combinations with fertility below 75% were considered partially sterile. Confirmatory tests in the 1996 wet season at IARI showed an average spikelet fertility ranging from 78% to 83% in F₁s involving crosses of JD8 with two japonica lines,